

INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS.

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Abstract: In this article, we analyze the importance of modern innovative pedagogues and the need for new use of communicative competence used in the educational process and student development.

Key words: Communicative competence, innovative approaches, Interactive teaching methods, Technologies, Projects and practices, Multimedia materials.

The main part: Changes in the economic and socio-cultural structures of countries, entering the world educational space required a revision. Specialist training methods and approaches. In the new education strategy, not only the reorientation of the system of knowledge and skills, but also the basic competences announced by the state in the intellectual and communication fields was carried out. In other words, the level of training of future specialists of the university is determined by their professional abilities, and socio-cultural adaptation in a rapidly changing world, knowledge and practical skills in establishing scientific intercultural relations, communication between different countries are an integral part of the professional culture of a specialist. This article examines the sociolinguistic aspect of communicative competence, which represents a complex of cultural knowledge.

Students work with innovative approaches in the development of communicative competence. Communicative competence is the ability to express information, understand concepts, and express one's ideas with consistency, including students' coherence.

The following innovative approaches can be used for this development:

- ❖ **Interactive teaching methods:** Teachers can use interactive teaching methods to develop students' communicative competence. For example, students can develop their communicative competence through expressing their opinions, group discussions and creative activities.
- ❖ **Technologies:** Through the use of new technologies, students can develop their communicative competence. Online platforms, video lessons, websites and mobile applications can provide opportunities for students to communicate, create creative programs and express their ideas.
- ❖ **Projects and internships:** Students can develop their communicative competence through projects and internships. For example, they can develop their communicative competence by working in the community in a group, creating projects and sharing their ideas with others.
- ❖ **Multimedia materials:** Teachers can help students develop their communicative competence through multimedia materials. Through videos, audio tracks, infographics and graphic materials, they can create an opportunity for students to coherently express information and understand concepts.

Interactive teaching methods are teaching methods used in order to increase students' activity, to express their thoughts and to create an opportunity for learning. Through these methods, teachers direct students to active learning and help develop their communicative competence. Interactive lesson methods can be implemented in the following ways:

- ✓ **Discussion and group work:** The teacher guides the students to discuss in groups, express their thoughts and share their thoughts with others. Through this method, students develop the ability to share their ideas with others, ask questions, and work in the community.
- ✓ **Role-playing:** Through role-playing, students are given an opportunity to challenge, consult and solve problems. Through this method, students can develop skills to understand most of other people, analyze the problem and find a solution to it.
- ✓ **Practical training:** Through practical training, students are given the opportunity to master and learn through practice. Through this method, students can develop the ability to apply theoretical knowledge, solve creative problems and work in society.
- ✓ **Use of technologies:** Through the use of technologies, it is possible to implement interactive teaching methods. Online platforms, video lessons, websites,

and mobile apps can provide interactive lessons to students, enabling them to coherently express information and understand concepts.

Conclusion: To solve such problems, it is necessary to retrain teachers, hold seminars, video conferences, webinars, organize multimedia cabinets, and conduct educational work among students on the use of modern computer technologies. The best option for introducing innovations into the higher education system is distance education through the use of global and local world networks.

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